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Physics-Informed, Data-Driven: A Hybrid Digital Twin for Metal Additive Manufacturing

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1. Introduction

Additive Manufacturing (AM) is moving from prototyping to certified production at scale. According to the industry, the market grew from \$18.0B in 2022 to \$20.0B in 2023 and \$21.9B in 2024, with forecasts pointing toward ~\$114.5B by 2034 [1]. Yet adoption is constrained by quality and efficiency gaps: many organisations still discover defects late, after long, expensive builds.

Against this backdrop, the Twin4Twin consortium has developed a Hybrid Digital Twin (HDT) for metal AM that brings together an instrumented Laser Power Bed Fusion (LPBF) machine, a real-time data backbone, physics-based reduced-order models, and AI-driven computer vision for in-process anomaly detection. The goal is to detect defects early, and reduce scrap and post-processing.

What follows is a decision-maker's guide to the opportunity and the solution.

Section 2

Quantifies the AM market outlook and growth dynamics that make in-process quality a priority.

Section 3

Summarises the problem and industry context driving demand for monitoring.

Section 4

- Unpacks the Twin4Twin HDT architecture.
- Details the LPBF testbed and data pipeline.
- Presents the physics and AI components with validation results.
- Translates technical performance into business value.

2. Market Outlook for AM

According to the Wohlers 2025 Report, the Additive Manufacturing (AM) market continues its steady climb: from \$18.0 billion in 2022 to ~\$20.0 billion in 2023 (~+11% YoY), reaching \$21.9 billion in 2024 (+9.1% YoY) [1]. Ten-year projections widen meaningfully with scale, according to the Wohlers 2025 Report, the AM market is forecasted to grow at a

Compounded Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of +18%, reaching \$114.5 billion by 2034 (see Fig. 1) [1]. The trajectory reflects growing installed base, materials breadth, and services/software penetration, as AM shifts from prototyping to certified production—conditions that reward in-process quality control technologies such as hybrid digital twins.

Fig. 1 Global AM market size [1]

Metal printers represent roughly one-third of the installed AM base: ~29.7% of printers in 2024 were metal (about 3,000 metal AM printers were sold in 2024), whereas 67.1% were polymer printers. Within metal printers, LPBF is the dominating production technology, accounting

for ~89.4% of metal printers—well ahead of binder jetting (~4.6%), DED-LB (~2.2%), PBF-EB (~2.1%), DED-arc (~1.5%), and MEX (~0.2%). This cements LPBF as the de facto platform for industrial metal AM and the prime target for in-process quality innovations.

Metal AM printers by production technology

Fig. 2 LPBF accounts for about 90% of metal AM printers [1]

3. Problem & Industry Context

Metal AM vendors repeatedly flag the same bottleneck: defects are too often discovered after long, expensive builds, when scrap and rework are hardest to absorb. Previous studies have found that 80% of the organisations report that quality issues and a lack of production efficiency, are major challenges that impede them from adopting AM [2]. Materialise frames it bluntly: *“Costs are compounded when scrap is identified too late in the production chain”* advocating layer analysis to catch issues during the job [3].

This has catalyzed a clear need for in-process monitoring, and AM machine builders are responding by embedding layer-by-layer sensing and analytics directly into their machines. EOS

offers Smart Monitoring aims to identify defects and spot process instabilities (e.g., extreme hot spots) as the build runs [4]. Similarly, RENISHAW has enabled in their metal AM machines real-time monitoring of AM performance using sensor feedback, surfacing errors during the build, as part of their AM Process Monitoring Suite [5]. In the same direction, Nikon has introduced in their machines a Layer Control System that continuously monitors the powder bed to detect coating irregularities layer-by-layer, aiming to identify problems before they cascade [6]. Hence, today the industry urgently needs robust in-process monitoring that identify defects as they form, so operators can intervene early rather than writing off part late in the chain.

4. The Twin4Twin Hybrid Digital Twin

The Twin4Twin HDT represents a novel integration of physics-based and data-driven modelling within a unified, scalable, and modular architecture for LPBF processes. Unlike conventional Digital Twins, which tend to emphasise either high-fidelity physics simulations or data-centric machine learning

models, the HDT developed under Twin4Twin synergistically fuses both paradigms, exploiting the different data modalities (in-situ process data and images), to enable predictive, interpretable, and real-time actionable intelligence to support decision-making.

Fig. 3 AconityMINI metal-3D printer serving as the testbed for the Twin4Twin HDT system.

4.1 HDT Technologies and test-bed

The Twin4Twin HDT employs the following technologies:

Physics-Based Core with Reduced-Order Models (ROMs)

The HDT incorporates advanced Finite Elements Modelling (implemented in Abaqus) to capture thermo-mechanical phenomena such as residual stress, distortion, and temperature distribution. To overcome computational costs, the high-fidelity results are condensed into Reduced

Order Models (ROMs) using Tensor Rank Decomposition (TRD). This allows predictive simulations to be executed in near real-time (range of milliseconds), supporting design-space exploration and process parameter optimisation.

AI-Driven Engine

A deep learning model that performs layer-by-layer defect detection in real time by using the high-resolution images from the in-situ camera. The model is trained on a high-quality

image dataset, carefully annotated and reviewed by experts, and achieves industrial-grade detection accuracy even with limited annotations.

Big-Data Infrastructure and Event-Driven Orchestration

The HDT leverages a microservices architecture, containerised via Docker, and an event-driven backbone using Apache Kafka for real-time communication between modules.

Multi-modal data (sensor time-series, pyrometer signals, images) are routed through InfluxDB and MinIO datalakes, enabling low-latency monitoring and long-term traceability.

Integrated Predictive-Observational Fusion

The innovation lies in cross-validating physics-based predictions with AI-driven defect observations. For example, predicted thermal-induced deformations are correlated with

visually detected recoater collisions, enabling robust anomaly detection and causal reasoning across digital and physical layers.

Towards Closed-Loop Control

While currently validated in open-loop mode, the HDT architecture has been designed to enable automatic feedback loops, where detected anomalies or predicted deviations trigger adaptive adjustments in

laser parameters, scan strategies, or recoating sequences. This provides a pathway to autonomous quality assurance and zero-defect manufacturing.

The HDT system is deployed on a Metal-3D printer LPBF testbed (AconityMINI, see Fig. 3), developed by ACONITY3D [7]. The machine features a 500 W infrared continuous-wave laser, paired with a two-axis galvo scanner and an f-theta lens. The build chamber includes a pre-heating system capable of reaching up to 800 °C (effective build area: Ø100 mm with

preheating, reduced from Ø140 mm without it). The AconityStudio software enables operators to load build job files and execute print jobs. Alternatively, an API is provided for Python-based control, which allows real-time data acquisition from the integrated sensors and dynamic parameter adjustments, e.g., changing laser power mid-process.

4.2 Hybrid Digital Twin Validation

The validation of the HDT was conducted to assess the consistency, accuracy, and interoperability between its two intelligence cores, the physics-based Finite Element Model (FEM), and the AI-powered computer vision model for in-process defect detection.

Physics-based FEM validation

An extensive validation campaign was performed on the AconityMINI testbed using the twin-cantilever as benchmark geometry. Finite Element thermo-mechanical simulations were performed in Abaqus following a Design-of-Experiments (DoE) matrix varying laser power, pre-heating temperature and scan speed. The simulation results were benchmarked against the actual experimental printing jobs and optical microscope measurements of vertical deflection. Across all tests, the model reproduced the temperature fields and the simulated deformation with a percentage error that ranges between 6 - 9% compared to the experimentally measured values, see Fig. 4.

Fig. 4 Deflection tip results simulated (δ) vs. experimental (δ^{EXP}) measurements for the different DoE tests.

AI-powered model validation

A state-of-the-art convolutional neural network architecture (YOLO) for real-time detection and segmentation was trained on a high-quality in-situ process image dataset annotated by domain experts. The image streams were captured layer-by-layer by a high-resolution camera. Several validation metrics were reported for the binary classification (defect/normal) (e.g. precision = 0.94, recall = 0.91, F1-score = 0.92) and the detection tasks (Mean Average Precision = 0.75), where inference latency was measured below 200 ms per frame on average. Finally, validation against post-build CT-scans and microscopy confirmed a high correlation between predicted and real defects (> 80% agreement), see Fig. 5.

Fig. 5 Model prediction against ground truth.

Overall, the fusion of heterogeneous data modalities and hybrid reasoning through FEM-derived predictions and AI intelligence, proved central to the HDT's capability. Cross-correlating simulated temperature gradients with detected thermal anomalies enhanced interpretability and causality analysis. For example, predicted local overheating zones aligned with regions where the AI model reported porosity-like patterns, improving confidence in root-cause identification and analysis.

5. Conclusions and next steps

The HDT developed for the Twin4Twin project represents a significant step towards the realisation of intelligent and resilient metal AM processes aligned with the core principles of Industry 4.0. The Twin4Twin HDT fuses physics-based simulation with AI-powered, in-process defect detection. Cross-correlating FEM-predicted thermal/deformation patterns with AI-detected anomalies improved interpretability and root-cause analysis.

Today, the HDT is validated in open-loop mode, with the architecture already prepared for feedback operation on the AconityMINI machine. Looking forward, advancements are foreseen in the following areas:

Transition from open-loop to closed-loop control, where the HDT's outputs will be used to automatically adjust process parameters during the print job to mitigate detected anomalies.

Broaden AI defect intelligence, by enhancing the AI model's capability to classify a wider range of defect types, and improve ROM's predictive power for more complex thermo-mechanical phenomena.

Benchmark performance, by validating HDT across alloys & geometries and enhancing ground-truth with Non-Destructive Testing techniques.

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